

Annual Review of Pharmacology and Toxicology
**Advancements in Assays for
 Micro- and Nanoplastic
 Detection: Paving the Way for
 Biomonitoring and Exposomics
 Studies**

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Keywords

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Abstract

Although plastic pollution and exposure to plastic-related compounds have received worldwide attention, health risks associated with micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) are largely unknown. Emerging evidence suggests MNPs are present in human biofluids and tissue, including blood, breast milk, stool, lung tissue, and placenta; however, exposure assessment is limited and the extent of human exposure to MNPs is not well known. While there is a critical need to establish robust and scalable biomonitoring strategies to assess human exposure to MNPs and plastic-related chemicals, over 10,000 chemicals have been linked to plastic manufacturing with no existing

standardized approaches to account for even a fraction of these exposures. This review provides an overview of the status of methods for measuring MNPs and associated plastic-related chemicals in humans, with a focus on approaches that could be adapted for population-wide biomonitoring and integration with biological response measures to develop hypotheses on potential health effects of plastic exposures. We also examine the exposure risks associated with the widespread use of chemical additives in plastics. Despite advancements in analytical techniques, there remains a pressing need for standardized measurement protocols and untargeted, high-throughput analysis methods to enable comprehensive MNP biomonitoring to identify key MNP exposures in human populations. This review aims to merge insights into the toxicological effects of MNPs and plastic additives with an evaluation of analytical challenges, advocating for enhanced research methods to fully assess, understand, and mitigate the public health implications of MNPs.

INTRODUCTION

Micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) are small plastic particles with a diameter of <5 mm (microplastics) and 1,000 nm (nanoplastics) that are formed during the use of plastic-containing materials, degradation and weathering of plastics, and intentional production for use in cleaning and personal-care products (1–4). The dramatic increase in plastic production over the past six decades has led to a widespread presence and potential for exposure to MNPs (5–7) and possible unknown implications for ecosystems and human health (8–14). The ubiquitous presence of MNPs in the environment has caused them to enter the food chain, which provides a direct pathway for human exposure (10, 15, 16). The detection of MNPs in human biological samples, such as feces, placenta, and breast milk, has confirmed human exposure to MNPs (15–21).

While exposure to plastics is ubiquitous, the health implications of exposure to complex mixtures of MNPs and plastic-related chemicals are not well known (10, 22, 23). To date, there has been extensive research on health impacts of select plastic additives (e.g., bisphenol A, phthalates); however, this represents only a fraction of the chemicals used in plastic manufacturing and does not inform how exposure to mixtures may lead to health effects. Although data on human health effects of exposure to MNPs are limited, several studies suggest a possible association between MNPs and adverse health outcomes (11, 24–30). The health risks posed by MNPs are likely further complicated by their high surface area-to-volume ratio and irregular morphology, which enable them to act as cotransporters for other hazardous substances, including endocrine-disrupting chemicals, persistent organic pollutants, and heavy metals (5, 20, 31, 32). Moreover, the detection of MNPs in human breast milk and placentas raises concern about infant exposure and the potential adverse impacts on offspring exposure from the mother (12, 15, 33).

A lack of robust and scalable analytical methods for biomonitoring MNPs has limited our ability to determine key MNP and plastic-related exposures in human populations. Despite methodological advancements in the measurement of MNPs from complex matrices, there is an urgent need for standardized laboratory protocols for biomonitoring MNPs and plastic-related chemicals. As such, efforts have been made to accurately determine the levels and characteristics of MNPs in various biological or environmental matrices (15, 17, 19, 22, 23, 34–37), while other research has focused on advancing the reliability and sensitivity of the chemical composition of MNPs. Advanced instrumentation methods, such as Raman and IR microspectroscopy, and hyphenated techniques, such as liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (LC/MS) and gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC/MS), have enabled the detailed

characterization of MNPs in terms of size, shape, polymer type, number of particles, and concentration (31, 35–39). However, protocols and standards for sample collection, quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC), analysis, and reporting (21, 34, 36, 39) have yet to be fully developed for human biospecimens. As a result, the processes of absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion of MNPs in the human body, as well as their presence across populations, remain unclear (12, 40).

In addition to MNPs, the extensive use of additives associated with plastic products has the potential to represent a significant exposure burden. It has been estimated that more than 10,000 chemicals are used during plastic production, and only a limited number of these chemicals have been evaluated for potential exposures or toxicological effects (7, 41–44). This initial accounting of plastic-related chemicals was further expanded by the PlastChem Project, which recently announced the identification of more than 16,000 chemicals used in the production of plastic materials (45). These chemicals include both intermediates necessary for the manufacture of plastic materials and additives that improve the performance and longevity of plastics. Additives play a critical role in the manufacture of plastic-containing materials and include antioxidants for maintaining the integrity of the polymer matrix against oxidative conditions, plasticizers for enhancing the flexibility of plastics, and flame retardants for fire resistance. Other additives, such as transition metal ion-containing polymerization catalysts, solvents, or lubricants, are essential for efficient manufacturing processes and for ensuring the quality of the final plastic product, but they also come with potential additional risks to the environment (41, 42, 46). While several methods have been validated to detect and quantify the most common plastic additives across various matrices (32, 47–49), significant limitations in the current methodological approaches remain, and targeted methods alone are often not able to capture the complexity of plastic-related exposures (7, 18, 50). Thus, given the large number of chemicals involved in plastic manufacturing and their limited toxicological data, we lack a comprehensive understanding of both exposures and effects of MNPs and other plastic-related chemicals in human populations (7, 43, 51).

In this review, we focus on the state of the science of MNP biomonitoring for identifying key plastic exposures and their potential toxicological effects. First, we provide an overview of the state of research on the toxicological effects of MNPs and plastic additives, emphasizing the potential translation for understanding effects of exposures in humans. Second, we examine the latest analytical methods used for characterizing MNPs and plastic additives and discuss the associated challenges and limitations of these methods. Finally, we highlight the importance of advancing exposome-based analytical strategies to achieve a comprehensive, scalable, and high-throughput measurement of MNPs and plastic-related chemical exposure burdens in human populations to inform the potential for affecting public health.

CURRENT UNDERSTANDING OF TOXICOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF MNPs AND PLASTIC ADDITIVES

MNPs and other plastic-related chemicals are attracting considerable attention as an exposure of concern due to their widespread occurrence in both commercial products and the environment, recalcitrant properties, and potential for adverse health effects (52, 53). Exposure routes, including ingestion, inhalation, and dermal contact, are important considerations in evaluating the effects of MNPs, as well as coexposure to related plastic additives (54, 55). The ubiquitous presence of MNPs in food, animal products, and drinking water highlights their integration into the human diet (56, 57). Existing studies have explored the adverse impact of MNPs on various biological systems, from aquatic organisms to mammalian cells to humans. To date, growing evidence suggests adverse outcomes related to multiple end points, including but not limited to increased

cardiovascular risk (58), cytotoxicity (59, 60), genotoxicity (61), immunotoxicity (62), oxidative stress and inflammation (63), gastrointestinal alternations and membrane injury (64), neurotoxicity (65, 66), and carcinogenicity (67), which have been associated with multiple polymer types and their degradation products. These studies, which include both *in vitro* and *in vivo* systems, support emerging evidence that MNPs may be associated with several toxicological mechanisms; however, translating this information to humans is challenging due to the difficulty in using model MNP exposures to represent complex exposures experienced from environmental MNPs. In addition, limited research exists on how MNPs may potentiate endocrine disruption, neurotoxicity, or carcinogenicity effects of plastic additives, such as plasticizers, flame retardants, and stabilizers (68).

Due to the large number of chemicals used as plastic additives, it is crucial to acknowledge that the existing toxicological studies cover only a fraction of the vast array of chemicals present in plastics. Thus, there is a large knowledge gap regarding the toxicity of plastic additives to humans and the environment. Furthermore, once these additives leach from plastics, exposure to sunlight and oxygen can transform them into different compounds that may have toxicological effects different from those of the parent compounds. As a result, the toxicity of various plastic formulations and their potential transformation products remains largely unknown. To address the gaps in our understanding, future research should prioritize elucidating the complex chemical landscape of plastics and identifying the key plastic exposures in human populations. Additionally, studies should focus on the most relevant exposure scenarios, considering the life cycle of plastics and their potential migration into food, air, and water sources. Assessing the cumulative effects of chronic exposure and exploring the impact of plastic degradation products will contribute to a more holistic understanding of the potential risks to human health.

OVERVIEW OF ANALYTICAL METHODS FOR MNPs AND PLASTIC ADDITIVES: ADVANCEMENTS AND CURRENT LIMITATIONS

Microscopy, a key strategy for studying MNPs, allows for measurement of particle morphology and composition (69). Microscopy techniques, including stereomicroscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and fluorescence microscopy, are instrumental in the qualitative and quantitative analysis of MNPs across different matrices. However, it is important to note that these techniques may not be as effective for MNPs in the nanometer range (<1,000 nm) due to their size falling below the resolution limit of conventional microscopes (16, 42, 69, 70). These methods offer insights into particle shape, size, and chemical composition when combined with vibrational spectroscopic techniques such as Raman spectroscopy and Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy (10, 71, 72).

Studies employing stereomicroscopy were some of the first to provide detection of MNPs in environmental and biological samples and allow for sorting and categorization of MNPs based on visible characteristics like shape and color (16, 42, 70). Further detailed morphological analysis through SEM has provided high-resolution images, which are crucial for examining particle surface textures and detecting additives or contaminants. This advanced imaging, at times augmented by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy, has offered insights into the potential sources of those polymers (9, 10, 71–73). Moreover, the integration of microscopy with Raman or FTIR microspectroscopy has facilitated the chemical characterization of microplastics, enhancing our comprehension of pollution sources and environmental distributions (23, 34, 74). The importance of robust statistical analysis for particle size distributions and polymer types combined with quality control measures such as blanks and recovery rate assessments has been key to ensure data reliability for these measurement techniques (36, 73, 75).

However, ongoing challenges limiting the use of these techniques in measuring MNPs on a larger scale, including difficulty in standardizing methodologies, decreasing detection limits, and differentiating between natural and synthetic particles, suggest further development is needed to fully take advantage of these approaches for MNP biomonitoring. Ongoing efforts are focused on the development of automated microscopy techniques for more efficient and unbiased particle analysis and the integration of novel spectroscopic methods for comprehensive polymer identification to address these challenges and enhance the accuracy of MNP discovery (34, 74).

Raman Microspectroscopy

Raman microspectroscopy has emerged as a critical analytical tool in MNP analysis (19, 21, 22, 24, 27, 31, 36, 70, 74, 76–84). The ability to detect particles of the submicron size range enables the detection of smaller particles compared with other microscopy methods. This method operates on the principle of inelastic photon scattering when a laser beam is targeted at a sample, with the resulting Raman spectrum providing fingerprints of the chemical composition of the particle (81, 85).

Raman microspectroscopy is also nondestructive and includes both qualitative and quantitative data about MNPs, such as polymer type, size, and concentration (19, 36, 70, 74, 76, 77, 82). Another advantage of Raman spectroscopy is its high sensitivity and resolution, especially in its advanced forms, such as surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (74, 77, 82) and stimulated Raman scattering microspectroscopy (79). However, Raman spectroscopy methods face several limitations, and one prominent limitation is the interference of colored or fluorescent particles with the Raman signal (86, 87). Raman spectroscopy is also limited by prolonged measurement times, which may affect its suitability for rapid or large-scale assessments (19, 36, 80, 85); the ability to analyze polymer mixtures (36, 76, 79, 81); and restricted detection of certain polymer types (24, 74). Consequently, it is often employed as an auxiliary detection method to provide additional information for polymer identification.

Raman spectroscopy has been used to quantify human exposure to MNPs. Cetin et al. (11) used Raman microspectroscopy to examine microplastics extracted from colon tissue samples. The analysis revealed increased concentration of microplastics in the tumoral colon tissues of patients diagnosed with colorectal adenocarcinoma when compared with normal colon tissues (11). The size of the microplastics isolated from these tissues varied from 1 to 1,299 μm , and they identified polyethylene (PE), poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA), and nylon(polyamide) MNPs (11). Horvatits et al. (24) used Raman microspectroscopy to detect microplastics in the liver of patients with cirrhosis and identified six types of microplastic polymers ranging in size from 4 to 30 μm . No MNPs were found in liver, kidney, and spleen samples from patients without liver disease, suggesting that accumulation of microplastics in the liver could potentially contribute to the development of fibrosis or are a result of cirrhosis and portal hypertension. Ragusa et al. (19) used Raman microspectroscopy and detected contamination in the breast milk of 34 women, with 26 samples containing predominantly PE, polyvinyl chloride, and polypropylene (PP) with particles ranging in size from 2 to 12 μm . This finding, coupled with the previous identification of MNPs in the human placenta, highlights the potential for early-life exposures (19).

Fourier Transform Infrared Microspectroscopy

FTIR microspectroscopy is another key technology for MNP identification (9, 23, 26, 38, 39, 71, 73, 83, 88–90). This technique measures the IR radiation absorbed by a sample for insight into its molecular composition. By detecting the vibrational frequencies of different chemical bonds,

FTIR microspectroscopy reveals distinct spectral fingerprints, allowing for precise identification of different polymer types through their absorption peaks in the FTIR spectrum (91).

FTIR microspectroscopy provides many advantages for measuring MNPs, including allowing for nondestructive analysis and providing spectra that can be evaluated for different molecular and functional groups in plastic polymers (31, 91). This attribute, combined with its time efficiency, makes FTIR microspectroscopy a more practical choice compared with other methods. Additionally, its sensitivity to the weathering processes of microplastics, and the study of how microplastics transport pollutants, improves our understanding of their degradation and environmental impact (91, 92).

FTIR microspectroscopy techniques are extensively used for detecting microplastic pollution in marine and freshwater ecosystems (10). Akoueson et al. (34) employed FTIR microspectroscopy to identify plastic particles in biota samples, revealing higher particle levels in fish gills and gut tissues. Scallop tissues displayed elevated, species-specific particle concentrations, and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and PE were the most detected microplastics (34). Besides, the FTIR microspectroscopy method has been applied to assess MNP exposure in humans (11, 21, 26).

FTIR microspectroscopy has also been used as a complementary MNP detection method in various studies that undertake comprehensive MNP analysis by integrating multiple analytical methods for measuring different aspects of MNP profiles. For example, Jung et al. (84) conducted a comprehensive analysis of common polymers using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)-FTIR-GC/MS and Raman spectroscopy toward a database for MNP identification, characterization, and quantitation.

Liquid Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry

LC/MS has been used extensively for characterizing plastic additives and leachates and has been recently combined with chemical depolymerization methods to measure MNPs in environmental and biological samples (12, 15, 21, 35, 47, 93–96). These approaches differ from microscopy-based methods in that they measure particle mass and burden rather than particle size or number. LC/MS is an analytical method that involves the separation of mixtures with multiple components using LC, where these components pass through a column filled with a solid adsorbent at varying rates, followed by MS analysis that ionizes these separated components and measures their mass-to-charge ratio. This combination is pivotal for the identification, characterization, and quantification of chemicals in complex mixtures (97). In the context of microplastics analysis, LC/MS stands out for its ability to detect plastics and additives; however, in order for MNPs to be measured by LC/MS, the particles must somehow be reduced to small-molecule signatures or individual monomers. By allowing for the detection of individual chemical constituents and individual monomers, LC/MS is well positioned for measuring MNPs in complex environmental samples and cotransported environmental pollutants. Additionally, LC/MS is applicable for quantitative analysis and is adaptable to various sample types, such as water, soil, and biological tissues (98).

Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry

GC/MS, which is designed for the analysis of volatile and semivolatile compounds, is another powerful platform for quantifying MNPs when combined with pyrolysis or other methods that first reduce the MNPs to characteristic fragments (99). In GC/MS, the volatile or semivolatile compounds are carried by an inert gas through a chromatographic column, and the compounds are separated on the basis of their interactions with the column's coating material at elevated temperatures. When exiting the column, compounds are ionized and then analyzed by the mass spectrometer, which provides a distinct mass spectrum for each compound. This unique spectral

data combined with chromatography retention time allow for precise identification and quantification of volatile or semivolatile substances present in the sample, making GC/MS a powerful tool in the identification of microplastic additives and leachates (32, 37, 44, 84, 96, 100–105).

Both LC/MS and GC/MS as standalone platforms are known for their effectiveness in chemical analysis and often function as supportive tools to analyze MNP additives or eluents. However, their application in the detection of plastic polymers in complex samples is somewhat limited, partly due to the need for extensive cleanup before analysis, the potential contamination by plastic-containing sample preparation consumables, and sample introduction methods.

Pyrolysis (Py)-GC/MS has recently emerged as one of the leading strategies for quantitative detection and characterization of microplastics in environmental and biological samples (8, 39, 43, 106–111). Py-GC/MS incorporates a built-in pyrolysis furnace to break down complex polymers into simpler products that can be measured by GC/MS. The pyrolysis furnace, operating at high temperatures in the absence of oxygen, effectively breaks down the polymers, and the resulting pyrolyzates are then injected into the gas chromatograph/mass spectrometer, which separates and identifies these compounds, allowing for precise polymer identification. Compared with other analysis methods, Py-GC/MS provides both qualitative and quantitative information about MNPs and can both identify and quantify the types of polymers and additive chemicals. Py-GC/MS is particularly powerful for analyzing complex environmental and biological samples like soil, water, and biota samples, which often contain a mixture of different MNPs and additives (107). Its ability to analyze bulk samples is also beneficial for large-scale biomonitoring assessments; however, the need for complex sample preparation and cleanup has limited use of this approach for large-scale biomonitoring efforts (112).

Py-GC/MS offers various approaches tailored to different research needs. Pyrolysis in Py-GC/MS can occur in two primary modes: pulse and continuous. Pulse mode involves introducing the sample in a cold state and then rapidly heating it to pyrolysis temperature, typically using a heated filament or Curie-point pyrolysis. Continuous mode, also called thermal desorption in some contexts, uses furnaces or microfurnaces for a more consistent heating profile. The choice between these modes and instruments depends on the desired speed and uniformity of pyrolysis. For instance, microfurnace pyrolysis, especially vertical microfurnace, is preferred for its rapid heating capabilities, improving the transfer of pyrolyzed samples onto the chromatographic column and enhancing peak resolution. Despite the variations, pyrolysis generally requires small sample sizes to ensure effective purging and avoid contamination in subsequent analyses (106).

Py-GC/MS has been widely used in the identification and quantification of polymers, especially in the simultaneous identification and quantification of polymer types and plastic additives. Zhou et al. (109) presented a comprehensive study of the analysis and extraction of MNPs in animal tissues. The authors employed Py-GC/MS to identify and quantify polystyrene (PS) and PMMA and demonstrated its reliability and sensitivity, with good linearity, reproducibility, and low limits of detection. Leslie et al. (110) employed Py-GC/MS to analyze samples from 22 healthy volunteers and successfully identified and quantified four major plastic polymers (PET, PE, PS, and PMMA), revealing an average concentration of 1.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Deshpande et al. (111) used Py-GC/MS as one of the analysis tools to analyze 115 plastic debris samples from the northern Gulf of Alaska, employing a two-tier approach for accurate chemical characterization. The authors found that low-density plastics like PE and PP were common in certain areas, suggesting oceanic origins, while a more varied composition of plastics was observed in western Prince William Sound, indicating both oceanic and terrestrial sources. Akoueson et al. (43) successfully employed Py/thermal desorption (TD)-GC-high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) to analyze organic plastic additives in food packaging, leading to the identification of 49 of 57 selected additive molecules. When applied to PP and polylactic acid food containers, this method detected

10 different types of additives, including plasticizers, antioxidants, and flame retardants, emphasizing the need for individual material safety assessments and greater transparency in plastic formulations (43).

Dynamic Light Scattering

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) is a technique commonly used to determine the size distribution of small particles in suspension or polymers in solution; however, it cannot separately detect particles of different origins or types. The method is based on the analysis of fluctuations in the scattering of laser light as it passes through a particle suspension. If plastic particles are separated from additional particles within a sample, DLS can be used to assess the size distribution of plastic particles (89, 109, 113). Caputo et al. (89) used DLS and multi-angle DLS (MADLS) to characterize PS particles. This study suggested that a limitation of the DLS method is its underestimation of larger particles in bimodal samples. DLS also struggled with reliably detecting the presence of different sized particles in mixtures, particularly in the range of 200 nm to 2 μ m (89).

Thermogravimetric Analysis

TGA is an analytical technique used to measure the weight change of a material as a function of temperature. The fundamental principle of TGA involves gradually heating a sample and recording its mass loss as the temperature increases. This mass loss typically occurs due to the evaporation of volatile components, decomposition, or oxidation of the material, which results in a weight loss curve that is unique to the material's composition (114). TGA provides an additional measurement strategy for MNPs, which can be accomplished by evaluating the weight loss curve of the analyzed polymers obtained from TGA. Moreover, when TGA is coupled with other analytical techniques like GC/MS, it allows for detailed characterization of gaseous degradation products, further aiding the precise identification of polymer types in microplastics (84, 87).

A Key Role for the Exposome in the Study of MNPs and Associated Health Effects

The past 15 years have seen rapid growth in the use of exposomics approaches to improve our understanding of how complex environmental exposures and other nongenetic factors contribute to disease risk. First defined by Wild (115) in 2005, the exposome was envisioned as a complement to the genome that aims to define an individual's history of exposure and relationship with disease risk, including the influence of lifestyle, diet, and the environment. Later redefined to include the cumulative measure of environmental influences and corresponding biological responses across the lifespan, the exposome aims to incorporate more comprehensive measures of complex environmental exposures with high-dimensional characterization of biological effects and molecular layers, which can be measured using 'omics and systems biology approaches (116). The application of exposome approaches to human populations has greatly benefited from the development of untargeted HRMS approaches that enable screening for a wide range of exogenous and endogenous compounds within biological samples (117–123). HRMS instruments, which enable high-resolution and accurate mass detection that enables prediction of chemical identification, also show sensitivity and dynamic range to detect low-level chemical exposures and drugs. While these approaches have been primarily applied to study overall exposure profiles, there exists a critical opportunity to combine untargeted analytical strategies with MNP measurement approaches to more comprehensively capture complex plastics exposures. For example, HRMS strategies can be used to identify novel plastic-related chemicals in plastic formulations, to characterize model plastic exposures for toxicological studies, and to apply an exposome-wide

Figure 1

Bridging MNP measurements in biological samples with exposomic tools provides a key framework for comprehensive exposure burden assessment. Abbreviations: FTIR, Fourier-transform infrared; LC-HRMS, liquid chromatography with high-resolution mass spectrometry; MNP, micro- and nanoplastics; Py-GC/HRMS, pyrolysis-gas chromatography/high-resolution mass spectrometry.

association study framework to identify and prioritize the top plastic exposures occurring in human populations (12). When MNP measurement techniques and chemical screening approaches are integrated within a systems biology framework (Figure 1), it is possible to identify hypotheses about potential mechanisms underlying MNP exposure–outcome relationships that can be evaluated using model systems.

While targeted methods provide excellent sensitivity and can generate new insight into identified exposures, the total number of chemicals that can be quantified is often limited by cost and sample constraints. Thus, the development of targeted exposome-level assays for comprehensive MNP biomonitoring is cost prohibitive and does not enable the detection of unknown and uncharacterized exposures for prioritizing key biomarkers of plastic exposure. Since untargeted analytical methods using HRMS maximize the number of chemicals that can be measured in a single sample, these approaches are optimal for developing exposome approaches for studying plastic exposures and MNPs. This section examines how untargeted analytical approaches have been used for studying MNP exposures to better understand exposure patterns and their associated toxicological effects, and how such advancements have the potential for development of new strategies for population-wide biomonitoring of MNPs.

Liquid Chromatography with High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry

Although traditionally used for targeted measurements of plastic-related chemicals, LC-HRMS has also been applied in the untargeted screening of plastic additives (50, 94, 95, 124) and nonintentionally added substances (NIASs) (48, 49). For example, Yusà et al. (48) focused on substances

migrating from polycarbonate bowls used in food contact scenarios. The authors adopted an untargeted method using LC-Orbitrap Tribrid-HRMS, which involved conducting migration tests with food simulants, replicating conditions akin to actual usage. To evaluate the safety of leached compounds, the researchers used the threshold of toxicological concern methodology. The results tentatively identified 24 substances, predominantly NIASS, in food contact polycarbonate items. These included mainly plasticizers, slip agents, antioxidants, UV stabilizers, and fragrances. Notably, most of these compounds had not been previously detected in polycarbonate materials used for food contact. Among these, only the slip agent hexadecanamide was found, but the identified compounds were generally not considered to pose a risk (48). With the development of chemical databases for screening packaging and plastic-related chemicals (7), there exist multiple opportunities for expanding screening methods to evaluate plastic-related compounds in blood; and when combined with recently developed methods for depolymerizing MNPs, such as alkaline-assisted hydrolysis, untargeted LC-HRMS holds great promise as a technological platform for studying complex plastic exposures.

Untargeted Analysis Using Gas Chromatography with Mass Spectrometry

As highlighted in the previous section, GC/MS supplements LC/MS in the chemical analysis of volatile and semivolatile compounds and is also applicable for untargeted analysis (44, 87, 101, 102, 125–127). Peñalver et al. (101) reported the analysis of multifloral honey samples using GC coupled with a quadrupole mass spectrometer in a hybrid targeted and nontargeted analysis mode. Eight multifloral honey samples from various suppliers and packaged in different materials were analyzed. Each honey sample was dissolved in water, and dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction (DLLME) was used to isolate leachates within the honey. The extracted phase was then analyzed by GC/MS using a full scan mode. The developed DLLME-GC/MS method was sensitive and reliable for detecting the migration of chemical compounds from PET and PS containers into the honey, with concentrations of target compounds ranging from 15.3 to 334 ng/g in the honey samples (101). Carrero-Carralero et al. (127) proposed an untargeted evaluation strategy for measuring plastic-related chemicals leaching from food packaging material by GC×GC-TOFMS (time of flight mass spectrometry). The application of two-dimensional chromatography enabled improved separation of plastic-related analytes based on their volatility and polarity. This approach led to the annotation of 107 migrant substances, consisting mainly of NIASS, leaving only 23 unidentified compounds. Furthermore, a comprehensive and searchable database containing 130 compounds was compiled as part of this study. A recent study by Nel et al. (87) reported the combination of GC/MS with other analytical approaches in an untargeted analysis for plastic polymer identification. In this study, GC/MS was used to analyze the evolved gas products from TGA. The results showed efficient analysis and identification of the compounds present in the evolved gases (87).

Untargeted Analysis Using Pyrolysis Gas Chromatography with High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry

Py-GC/HRMS is highly suitable for untargeted analysis due to its ability to decompose and analyze complex samples without prior knowledge of their composition, which makes it invaluable to biomonitoring for large population studies, where the objective is often to explore a wide range of unknown compounds in biological samples. When incorporated within a workflow that enables reproducible and robust extraction and detection of MNPs in tissues, Py-GC/HRMS has the potential to provide critical data on the presence of MNPs and associated co-exposures (Figure 2). By breaking down unknown MNPs into smaller, identifiable molecules,

Figure 2

Demonstration of a Py-GC/HRMS analytical workflow for measuring MNP exposure profiles in human placenta. (Step ①) The collected placenta samples are uniformly dissected into small aliquots. (Step ②) These aliquots then undergo microwave-assisted extraction using an organic solvent to efficiently extract MNPs from the biological matrix. (Steps ③–⑤) The resulting liquid extract is pretreated by centrifugation before analysis using Py-GC/HRMS to identify polymers and additives. Abbreviations: MNP, micro- and nanoplastic; Py-GC/HRMS, pyrolysis gas chromatography with high-resolution mass spectrometry.

Py-GC/HRMS can detect and identify a range of compounds, including unexpected or unknown substances. Combined with high-resolution mass spectrometers, it is possible to assign molecular composition to pyrolytic products to predict the potential identities of the original polymer. This comprehensive profiling capacity is crucial for biomonitoring, as it allows researchers to detect and quantify a broad spectrum of environmental pollutants in biological matrices, such as tissues or bodily fluids. The use of Py-GC/HRMS, alongside other untargeted analysis instruments, such as LC-HRMS, can reveal new emerging contaminant products that were previously unknown, which is crucial for evaluating environmental exposure and potential health risks (12, 20, 106, 128).

Another strength of Py-GC/HRMS is that it is not limited by particle size, unlike many other visualization-based analytical techniques, allowing for the detection of MNPs arising from a diverse array of particle sizes. Detection of smaller MNPs is especially critical in human populations, since these particles are most likely to traverse biological membranes. Thus, Py-GC/HRMS methods are a key component for comprehensive assessment of MNPs in humans, and the development of workflows that enable rapid and efficient analysis of MNPs is critical (128).

Currently, there are no examples of using Py-GC/HRMS in the literature, and most studies performing untargeted analysis have relied on unit resolution instruments for untargeted analysis. Gao et al. (39) proposed a novel extraction protocol of nano-PS from biological samples. Tandem Py-GC/MS demonstrates a robust performance in the identification and quantification of PS in various sample types (43, 128). The method isolates the trimer of PS to estimate PS levels, using the selective ion monitoring mode to enhance specificity and reduce interference. With this approach, the limit of detection and limit of quantification for 70-nm PS were determined to be 0.0018 μg

and 0.0060 μg , respectively (39). Deshpande et al. (111) used untargeted analysis of Py-GC/MS to analyze plastic debris collected from the Gulf of Alaska, focusing on diverse physical characteristics. The pyrograms obtained from the Py-GC/MS analysis were compared with a library of known pyrograms for common polymers. This comparison enables the identification of the composition of the collected plastic debris. This study showcased the application of Py-GC/MS for identifying marine plastic pollution, a crucial technique in the realms of environmental monitoring and pollution control (111).

CONCLUSIONS

Opportunities and Limitations of Current MNP Detection Methods

In the earlier sections of this review, we explored MNP analysis methods and reviewed the current state of research. Notably, current detection methodologies, which rely predominantly on visual and spectroscopic approaches, encounter substantial challenges. These methods, including commonly used techniques such as Raman microspectroscopy and FTIR microspectroscopy, not only are labor-intensive but may be limited to the type of MNPs that can be detected. They struggle to detect a broad range of microplastic particles and various polymer types (11, 22, 26, 31, 76, 81). The primary focus of these techniques is the identification of microplastic particles and particle counts.

Moreover, microscope-based techniques cannot independently detect plastic additives without integration with other analytical instruments such as LC/MS or GC/MS, each of which requires specific sample preparation protocols (35, 47, 84, 100, 103). Thus, it is likely that complementary methods will be needed to assess MNPs and related chemicals in biological samples (**Figure 1**). An integrated comprehensive approach that covers polymer types, concentrations, and associated plastic additives is essential for a complete understanding and effective monitoring of microplastic pollution and its implications. This limitation in detection technology has resulted in a substantial gap in our understanding of MNP exposure in humans.

A key challenge in establishing robust measurement techniques for MNPs is the development of appropriate QA/QC procedures. Plastics are ubiquitous in the manufacture of chemical reagents; glassware; solvents; and in all steps of the sample collection, processing, and analytical workflows. Thus, it is critical to develop appropriate QA/QC plans, workflows, and reference materials that allow for the reduction of contamination while analyzing samples for MNPs and plastic-related chemicals. Additional guidance on lot-testing, cleaning, and appropriate handling procedures is also necessary. Finally, the development of proficiency testing protocols and materials will also be necessary for validating MNP measurements from different laboratories.

Future Directions

There is a critical role for the development and application of untargeted analytical approaches for studying MNP exposures and integrating exposure and effect measures within an exposome framework. For example, untargeted LC-HRMS methods facilitate the screening of both known plastic additives and NIAs by extracting candidate chemicals from various sample types, such as biological samples or environmental matrices. These methods enable the identification and quantification of compounds arising from plastic exposures, providing valuable insights into exposure sources and potential risks associated with plastic additives in different contexts, such as food contact scenarios and environmental contamination, while Py-GC/HRMS allows for the simultaneous identification and quantification of plastic polymers and additives and allows for screening for thousands of other plastic polymers (39, 109, 110). Integrating these untargeted screening methods with additional MNP characterization methods has the potential to vastly increase the

identification of a broader spectrum of MNP pollutants and their additives. The application of untargeted LC-HRMS and Py-GC/HRMS as a platform for exposome research could therefore provide invaluable insights into the microplastic burden in humans.

In conclusion, there is a critical need to advance the ability to characterize complex MNP exposures in humans. Development of untargeted analysis methods to expand the measurement of complex plastic exposure profiles, combined with leveraging a multi-omics strategy to understand the potential health effects of these exposures, provides a key strategy for studying MNPs and their effects in human populations. The combination of MNP analysis and exposomics studies holds great promise of uncovering the broader impacts of plastic pollution on human health and the environment, allowing for the development of effective strategies for pollution control and public health promotion.

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The authors are not aware of any affiliations, memberships, funding, or financial holdings that might be perceived as affecting the objectivity of this review.

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